

Progress and Obstacles in the Education of Women with Disabilities

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Abstract: I want to show in my research that people from all walks of life should participate in the overall development of this human civilization. Discrimination between men and women has been going on since that time. The path to women's education is already slippery. The problem of women with disabilities is much more complex and deep, better to say distance from civil society. However, women with disabilities have progressed along with women's education to build an inclusive society in the journey of society's progress. However, women with disabilities are deprived of individual freedom and the roof of a better society due to the lack of elimination of all discrimination in the patriarchal society. Along with social evolution, I have tried to highlight various ups and downs in education of women with disabilities.

Keywords: women's education, civil society, women with disabilities.

1. INTRODUCTION

Education is one of the main foundations or pillars of any civilized society. The development of human civilization has been accelerated by the educated class of the civilization. On the other hand, all the measures of the society which are signs of an underdeveloped society can be found to be due to lack of education. For example, lack of education is the root of all the superstitions and evil reforms in the society .

People from all walks of life should participate in the overall development of this human civilization. woman-Discrimination against men has been going on since that time. The path to women's education is already slippery. The problem of women with disabilities is much more complex and deeper than the civilized society. However, women with disabilities have progressed along with women's education by joining them to build an inclusive society. But complete elimination of discrimination in a patriarchal society no Because of this, women with disabilities are deprived of personal freedom and the pursuit of a better society. social evolution of As well as education of women with disabilities in case various I discuss the ups and downs below In short I will try to explain .

Research question

1. Government's Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan scheme how much help in the field of education for disabled women did _ 2. Has the Right to Education or RPD (Rights of Persons with Disabilities Act, 2016) provided by the Indian Constitution helped women with disabilities at all ?
3. To what extent is the government ensuring the participation of women with disabilities in technical education? successful ?

2. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

From this survey I will try to reveal the attitudes of women with disabilities. An evaluation of the various existing data in this field and their relevance to this work will follow. Here the data will be used primarily. For example interviews field work , manuscripts , dictionaries etc. will be used. Also I will take help from textbooks , magazines , internet possible chapter.

Chapter division

Chapter I: Brief history of the evolution of education for women with disabilities . Chapter II Importance and relevance of women with disabilities in technical education And the third chapter deals with problems and possible solutions in the education of women with disabilities.

3. CONCLUSION

From the above discussion we can conclude that there is no chance of neglecting women with disabilities in building an overall development oriented or inclusive society. Just as an estuary is formed when a river is obstructed in its own course, i.e. the river loses its rhythm, in the same way the absence of a class in a rapidly changing society causes a loss of rhythm in the progress of civilization. Education of women with disabilities is an essential part of society's demands and civilization today.

REFERENCES

- [1] Tuomi , Margaret Trotta, Elina Lehtomäki , and Magreth Matonya . "As capable as other students: Tanzanian women with disabilities in higher education." *International Journal of Disability, Development and Education* 62.2 (2015): 202-214 .(1)
- [2] Holloway, Sarah. "The experience of higher education from the perspective of disabled students." *Disability & Society* 16.4 (2001): 597-615 .(2)
- [3] Jameel, Syed Salma. "Disability in the context of higher education: Issues and concerns in India." *Electronic Journal for Inclusive Education* 2.7 (2011): 3.(3)
- [4] Mir, Afaq Ahmad, and Abdul Waheed . "Experiences of students with disabilities in Indian Higher Education: an interpretative phenomenological study." *Higher Education for the Future* 9.2 (2022): 186-202 .(4)
- [5] Saksena , Shalini, and Rashmi Sharma. "Deconstructing barriers to access higher education: A case study of students with disabilities in University of Delhi." *The Delhi University Journal of Undergraduate Research and Innovation* 1.2 (2015): 316- 337.(5)
- [6] Jameel, Syed Salma. "Disability in the context of higher education: Issues and concerns in India." *Electronic Journal for Inclusive Education* 2.7 (2011): 3.(6)
- [7] Palan , Ruchi. "'I seriously wanted to opt for science, but they said no': visual impairment and higher education in India." *Disability & Society* 36.2 (2021): 202-225.
- [8] Halder, Santoshi. "Prospects of higher education of the challenged women in India." *International Journal of Inclusive Education* 13.6 (2009): 633-646.
- [9] Lakshmana, CM, and I. Maruthi . "THE DISABLED POPULATION AND THEIR EDUCATIONAL STATUS IN INDIA." *Periphery* 10.2 (2018): 135-157.
- [10] Dawn, Ranjita . "ACCESSIBILITY TO HIGHER EDUCATION FOR PERSONS WITH DISABILITIES IN INDIA."
- [11] Evans, Nancy J., et al. *Disability in higher education: A social justice approach* . John Wiley & Sons, 2017.
- [12] Paul, Stanley. "Students with disabilities in higher education: A review of the literature." *College Student Journal* 34.2 (2000): 200-211.
- [13] Dolmage , Jay T. *Academic ableism: Disability and higher education*. University of Michigan Press, 2017.
- [14] Ahmad, Wasim. "Higher education for persons with disabilities in India: Challenges and concerns." *Journal of Disability Management and Rehabilitation* (2016): 1–4.
- [15] Kimball, Ezekiel W., et al. "Students with disabilities in higher education: A review of the literature and an agenda for future research." *Higher education: Handbook of theory and research* (2016): 91–156.
- [16] Mathews, Julie. "Empowering Disabled Women in Higher Education 1." *Changing the subject* . Taylor & Francis, 2017. 138-145.
- [17] Kunnath , Suja Kurian, and Samuel N. Mathew. "Higher education for students with disabilities in India: Insights from a focus group study." *Higher Education for the Future* 6.2 (2019): 171-187.
- [18] Zahid, Gulnaz , Aamna Saleem Khan, and Zehra Keshf . "Services for students with disabilities at higher education of Pakistan." *European Journal of Education Studies* (2018).
- [19] Palan , Ruchi. "'I seriously wanted to opt for science, but they said no': visual impairment and higher education in India." *Disability & Society* 36.2 (2021): 202-225.